

ELIXIR Commissioned Service

Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens (BFSP), WP3

M3.5 Hackathon in Freiburg

Tier: Science

Priority Area: Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens (BFSP)

Executive Summary

This Milestone presents the activities and outcomes related to the FAIRyMAGs Hackathon, which took place in Freiburg, Australia, and online from October 6–9, 2025. The event brought together researchers, developers, and data scientists from across the MAGs communities to collaborate on improving tools and workflows for the analysis of metagenome-assembled genomes (MAGs). A detailed blog post summarizing the hackathon outcomes is provided in Deliverable D3.5.

The Milestone describes the preparation, organization, and execution of the hackathon. It also highlights the main objectives and achievements of the event.

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

MAGs	metagenome-assembled genomes
IUC	Intergalactic Utilities Commission
IWC	Intergalactic Workflow Commission

FairyMAGs Hackathon October 6–9, 2025

Outline

The hybrid event took place from October 6–9, 2025, with participants joining from Freiburg (Germany), Australia, and online. A total of 23 researchers participated in the event, coordinated by Paul Zierep and Bérénice Batut, with support from Tiff Nelson at the Australian outpost.

Organization and Participation

The event was publicly announced via a Galaxy blog post (<https://galaxyproject.org/events/2025-10-06-fairy-ma-gs-hackathon/>) and by de.NBI (<https://www.denbi.de/training-courses-2025/1884-fairymags-hybrid-hackathon-2025-optimising-metagenomics-assembled-genomes-building>). It was open to the public but limited to 30 participants, and registration was available to anyone interested.

The event was promoted through several channels, including the ELIXIR Metagenomics and Biodiversity Community, the Galaxy Training Network (GTN), the BFSP Slack channel and meetings, and direct outreach to MAGs-related communities such as nf-core mag and microbial-bioinfo.slack.com. It was also highlighted at conferences such as the European Galaxy Days (EGD) (<https://galaxyproject.org/events/2025-10-01-egd2025/>), the ELIXIR All Hands Meeting (<https://www.france-bioinformatique.fr/en/news/recap-of-the-elixir-all-hands-meeting-2025-in-thessaloniki/>), and the CE-IUSSI Meeting 2025 in Szeged (<https://galaxyproject.org/news/2025-08-27-galaxy-at-ce-iussi/>, <https://f1000research.com/slides/14-1070>).

In total, 43 people registered for the event. Of those, 28 confirmed their participation, and 23 actively took part in the hackathon.

Preparation for the hackathon involved collaborative planning through a shared document. The event was structured around topic-focused days, where participants discussed the current state of the project and engaged in in-depth sessions. The focus days covered the following topics:

Monday

- Building intelligent computational resource estimation tools

Tuesday

- Enhancing FAIR MAGs building workflows
- Developing user-friendly training materials

Wednesday

- Advancing workflow evaluation methods
- Extra session: BRC-Analytics Corporation

The original schedule was adjusted during the event to meet participant needs. The “Building intelligent computational resource estimation tools” session was moved to Monday due to high community interest. Tuesday featured two focused topics to allow shared discussion with the Australian outpost. Finally, an additional topic was introduced on Wednesday to discuss collaboration with the BRC-Analytics project (<https://brc-analytics.org/>, <https://www.biorxiv.org/content/10.1101/2025.10.13.682095v1>), coinciding with a visit from Anton Nekrutenko (Lead of BRC-Analytics from Penn State University) to the Freiburg Galaxy Team.

Tiff Nelson organized a dedicated Australian outpost that worked on tasks in a time-shifted manner coordinated with the main event. The hackathon included joint Europe–Australia sessions during overlapping hours and Europe-focused working groups in the afternoons.

A dedicated Slack channel within the Galaxy Training Network workspace facilitated continuous communication and coordination throughout the event.

Major outcomes

Details of the hackathon outcomes are listed in the [✚ FAIRyMAGs Hackathon - Coordination & Tracking](#) sheet and are summarized in the blog post stated in Deliverable D3.5.

The FAIRyMAGs Hackathon achieved major progress in improving workflows, benchmarking standards, and training resources for metagenome-assembled genomes (MAGs). The team made substantial enhancements to workflows, including updating key tools such as SemiBin2, COMEBin, MaAsLin3, CheckM2, and GTDB-Tk. Several workflows were developed and refined, covering quality control, contamination removal, and fallback recovery, as well as new adaptations for long-read sequencing data. The main MAGs workflow was updated with user-friendly annotations and fixes to subworkflow bugs, and modular visualization plots were created. In collaboration with the MGnify team, work also began on a MAGs submission workflow, and the inclusion of FAIRyMAGs tools and databases on usegalaxy.org.au expanded accessibility for researchers in Australia.

In parallel, the group focused on creating comprehensive and user-friendly training materials. They began drafting a complete tutorial for running the full MAGs workflow on both short and long reads, while existing tutorials for assembly and binning were updated to include missing tools. A new tutorial was also introduced to guide users through preprocessing for group assignment and co-assembly. Together, these efforts form a structured learning pathway to help researchers use the workflows from preprocessing to downstream analysis.

Benchmarking and workflow evaluation were another key area of progress. The team collaborated with MGnify, nf-core/mag, and MAGNETO developers to align on standardized benchmarking datasets and procedures, using real data from the CAMI II challenge (https://frl.publisso.de/data/frl:6425521/plant_associated/) and Loman Lab Mock Community experiments (<https://lomanlab.github.io/mockcommunity/>). They finalized an amber-based (amber is a dedicated metagenome benchmarking tool) benchmarking workflow that allows to measure the performance of individual binners. They also evaluate MAG quality and performance using checkm2 for the real-world use cases, including marine, termite, and cloud datasets.

Finally, the hackathon team worked on improving resource estimation for Galaxy workflows. By analyzing performance data from MGnify and exploring the relationship between sample metadata and memory usage, they gained valuable insights into optimizing computational efficiency. However, they also identified a current limitation in Galaxy's ability to dynamically assign computational resources based on workflow-generated parameters. Discussions are ongoing with Galaxy core developers to explore workarounds and long-term solutions.

Supporting Documents

Announcement of the event:
<https://galaxyproject.org/events/2025-10-06-fairy-ma-gs-hackathon/> and

 galaxyproject-org-events-2025-10-06-fairy-ma-gs-hackathon-....pdf

Blog post of the event:
<https://galaxyproject.org/news/2025-10-21-fairymags-hackathon-outcome/> and

 galaxyproject-org-news-2025-10-21-fairymags-hackathon-outcome-... (1).pdf

Organization document of the event:
 FAIRyMAGs Hackathon - Organization document

Hackathon coordination and tracking sheet:
 FAIRyMAGs Hackathon - Coordination & Tracking

Dissemination Plans

The outcome of the Hackathon is disseminated via the blog post. Tool updates will be available to the community through code updates in Intergalactic Utilities Commission (IUC) (<https://github.com/galaxyproject/tools-iuc>) and subsequent automated updates on the Galaxy servers. The workflow updates will be published via IWC (Intergalactic Workflow Commission) (<https://github.com/galaxyproject/iwc>) and, in parallel, automatically on WorkflowHub. The use cases will be highlighted in Deliverable D3.2 and eventually published with M3.6.